

Desalination

Thermodynamic assessment of forward osmosis as pretreatment to boost the thermal efficiency and sustainability of multi-effect distillation for seawater desalination --Manuscript Draft--

Manuscript Number:	
Article Type:	Full Length Article
Section/Category:	Energy consumption and energy recovery
Keywords:	Forward Osmosis; Multi-effect distillation; Thermal Efficiency; Scaling; Sensitivity Analysis; Exergy Analysis
Corresponding Author:	Bartolomé Ortega-Delgado, Ph.D. Centro de Investigaciones Energeticas Medioambientales y Tecnologicas Departamento de Energia Tabernas, Almería SPAIN
First Author:	Bartolomé Ortega-Delgado, Ph.D.
Order of Authors:	Bartolomé Ortega-Delgado, Ph.D. Patricia Palenzuela, Ph.D. Ali Altaee, Ph.D. Diego-César Alarcón-Padilla, Ph.D. Alaa Al Hawari, Ph.D. Guillermo Zaragoza, Ph.D.
Abstract:	This work presents the thermodynamic assessment of a forward osmosis – multi-effect distillation (FO-MED) system able to improve the thermal performance of the MED seawater desalination process and reduce its environmental impact. The FO reduces the divalent ion concentrations that cause scaling, allowing to reach higher top brine temperatures. A sensitivity energy and exergy analysis has been carried out to identify the best boundary conditions that enhance the process efficiency, predicting the scale formation with the Ryznar index. Results show that the use of FO pretreatment in a conventional MED plant of 8 effects at 65 °C allows increasing the heating steam temperature up to 100 °C and the number of effects to 16 without increasing the risk of scaling. This results in a 50% reduction of the specific thermal energy consumption, a 19% decrease of the pumping power consumption, and an 8.1% decrease of the specific heat transfer area. The environmental impact is reduced by decreasing a 42% the volume of saline water rejected to the sea and a 37% the water footprint. The overall recovery ratio is increased from 9% to 15%. Finally, the exergy analysis reveals that the MED is the component with the highest exergy destruction.
Suggested Reviewers:	Andrea Cipollina, Ph.D. Associate Professor, Università degli Studi di Palermo: Università degli Studi di Palermo andrea.cipollina@unipa.it Dr Cipollina has extensive expertise in modelling multi-stage flash and multi-effect distillation processes, along with membrane desalination processes. He could perform a fair and meaningful review of the manuscript. Pierre Le Clech, Ph.D. Associate Professor, University of New South Wales p.le-clech@unsw.edu.au Dr Pierre Le Clech is a Chemical Engineer with a PhD from the University of Cranfield, UK. He is an expert in water and wastewater treatments by membrane processes, therefore he could do a comprehensive review of the manuscript. Raed Al-Juboori, Ph.D. Postdoctoral researcher, Aalto University Department of Chemistry: Aalto-yliopisto Kemian laitos raed.al-juboori@aalto.fi

	Dr Raed Al-Juboori has a BSc in Chemical Engineering, MENR in Environmental Engineering and PhD in Chemical Environmental Engineering. He is an expert in water treatment, water and wastewater engineering and membrane filtration processes.
Opposed Reviewers:	

Almería, 21 February 2022

Editor
Desalination

Dear Editor,

Attached you can find the manuscript:

“Thermodynamic assessment of forward osmosis as pretreatment to boost the thermal efficiency and sustainability of multi-effect distillation seawater desalination process”

Authors: B. Ortega-Delgado, P. Palenzuela, A. Altaee, D.-C. Alarcón-Padilla, A. H. Hawari and G. Zaragoza.

Please, consider the manuscript for possible publication as full length article in Desalination Journal. The main value of this article from our point of view is that it proposes a method to not only improve the thermal efficiency of the MED desalination process, but also to reduce its environmental impact by decreasing the water footprint and the volume of saline water disposal to the sea. Thus, this scheme is particularly interesting for brine treatment in sustainable desalination applications.

An added value of our manuscript is that, to the best of the authors’ knowledge, it is the first time in scientific literature that a comprehensive energy and exergy analysis of the FO process as a pretreatment is presented to investigate the operating and design conditions of the system leading to the maximum thermal efficiency of the MED seawater desalination process. We believe that this topic fits perfectly in the scope of the journal and will appeal to Desalination readers.

I look forward to hearing from you soon,

Bartolomé Ortega-Delgado

Postdoc Researcher
Solar Thermal Applications Unit
Plataforma Solar de Almería,
Carretera de Senés km. 4; P.O.BOX 22, 04200 Tabernas (Almería), Spain
Phone: (+34) 950 387 900 Ext 973, Fax: (+34) 950 365015
Email: bartolome.ortega@psa.es URL: www.psa.es

1. The hybridization of forward osmosis and multi-effect distillation is investigated
2. Forward osmosis pretreatment reduces the divalent ions from feedwater by ~40%
3. The specific thermal consumption is reduced by 50% and pumping power by 19%
4. The environmental impact of the brine disposal is reduced by 42% in volume
5. The highest exergy destruction occurs in the multi-effect distillation unit

Graphical Abstract

1 **Thermodynamic assessment of forward osmosis as pretreatment** 2 **to boost the thermal efficiency and sustainability of multi-effect** 3 **distillation for seawater desalination**

4
5 B. Ortega-Delgado¹, P. Palenzuela^{1,2}, Ali Altaee³, D.-C. Alarcón-Padilla^{1,2}, A.H. Hawari⁴,
6 G. Zaragoza^{1,2}

7 ¹CIEMAT-Plataforma Solar de Almería
8 Ctra. de Senés s/n, 04200 Tabernas, Almería, Spain

9
10 ²CIESOL-Universidad de Almería
11 Ctra, Sacramento s/n, Almería, 04120, Spain.

12
13 ³University of Technology Sydney
14 School of Civil and Environmental Engineering
15 Ultimo, NSW 2007, Australia

16 ⁴Department of Civil and Architectural Engineering
17 Qatar University, P.O. Box 2713, Doha, Qatar
18

19 **ABSTRACT**

20 This work presents the thermodynamic assessment of a forward osmosis – multi-effect
21 distillation (FO-MED) system able to improve the thermal performance of the MED seawater
22 desalination process and reduce its environmental impact. The FO reduces the divalent ion
23 concentrations that cause scaling, allowing to reach higher top brine temperatures. A sensitivity
24 energy and exergy analysis has been carried out to identify the best boundary conditions that
25 enhance the process efficiency, predicting the scale formation with the Ryznar index. Results
26 show that the use of FO pretreatment in a conventional MED plant of 8 effects at 65 °C allows
27 increasing the heating steam temperature up to 100 °C and the number of effects to 16 without
28 increasing the risk of scaling. This results in a 50% reduction of the specific thermal energy
29 consumption, a 19% decrease of the pumping power consumption, and an 8.1% decrease of the
30 specific heat transfer area. The environmental impact is reduced by decreasing a 42% the
31 volume of saline water rejected to the sea and a 37% the water footprint. The overall recovery

32 ratio is increased from 9% to 15%. Finally, the exergy analysis reveals that the MED is the
33 component with the highest exergy destruction.

34

35 **Keywords**

36 Forward Osmosis; Multi-Effect Distillation; Thermal Efficiency; Scaling; Sensitivity Analysis;
37 Exergy Analysis

38 **1 Introduction**

39 Water scarcity represents one of the biggest challenges for the immediate future worldwide.
40 Over two billion people (25% of the world population) suffer from water stress. It is estimated
41 that four billion people experience severe water scarcity at least one month during the year.
42 Seawater desalination is a feasible solution to mitigate this problem and reduce the depletion of
43 freshwater resources, mainly caused by agriculture (69%) [1]. The global contracted
44 desalination capacity reaches 100 million m³/d, mostly in MENA and East Asia countries, and
45 is led by membranes technologies [2]. Despite the current dominance of reverse osmosis (RO)
46 in the seawater desalination market, representing up to 66% of the installed capacity [3], thermal
47 processes such as multi-effect distillation (MED) still have a niche for high salinity feed and
48 harsh waters, but the technology needs some improvements to achieve techno-economic
49 viability. The higher energy consumption of MED compared with RO is one of its main
50 drawbacks. Increasing the top brine temperature (TBT) beyond the current scaling limit would
51 allow for incorporating more MED effects to raise the thermal efficiency and thus be more
52 competitive. However, this TBT is currently limited to around 65 – 70 °C due to the salt
53 precipitation occurring at higher temperatures that provoke scale deposits in the heat exchangers
54 of the MED unit. This phenomenon reduces the heat transfer in the distillation process and

55 eventually the overall freshwater production. One of the possible solutions is the use of
56 pretreatments able to reduce the divalent ions concentration present in the seawater entering the
57 MED plant, such as Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} and SO_4^{2-} , which are responsible for the scale formation in the
58 MED unit since their solubility decrease with the temperature, being more pronounced beyond
59 65 – 70 °C.

60 Some research works about using pretreatments to remove divalent ions for thermal
61 desalination can be found in the scientific literature. Hassan et al. [4] investigated the use of
62 nanofiltration (NF) as a pretreatment for removing scale-forming hardness ions and reducing
63 the TDS, which allowed elevating the temperature in multi-stage flash (MSF) plants and
64 improving their efficiency. A significant reduction of the energy consumption by 25 – 30% was
65 achieved, allowing the operation of the MSF plant at 120 °C without antiscalant addition to the
66 feedwater. Hamed [5] reported a successful hybridization of MSF and NF at pilot plant level
67 (20 m³/d) operating at 130 °C, at Al-Jubail water and power dual purpose plant (Saudi Arabia).
68 It was also pointed out that MED-NF schemes could increase the performance of this thermal
69 desalination process by operating at 125 °C. The high interest in NF-MED hybridization was
70 also highlighted by Altmann et al. [6]. They reported that the NF-MED configuration could
71 allow the MED to be operated at a TBT of 125 °C, increasing its thermal efficiency and reducing
72 the size with respect the standalone MED.

73 However, one of the main drawbacks of NF is that it requires feed pressure pumping (15 – 25
74 bar) [7], which means high energy consumption and thus elevated costs [8]. Another
75 pretreatment with high potential for thermal processes is forward osmosis (FO), which does not
76 need external hydraulic pressure to operate, as in the case of NF. It induces water permeation
77 from a low concentrated (called feed solution, FS) to a highly concentrated (called draw
78 solution, DS) through a semipermeable membrane due to the osmotic pressure gradient between
79 both solutions. As a result, the draw solution is diluted, and the feed solution is concentrated.

80 The use of FO as a pretreatment for MED is an environmentally friendly technology that
81 accounts for a series of advantages that allows reducing the environmental impact of
82 desalination. Usually, the brine generated in the desalination process is rejected back to the sea,
83 which is a major threat to the ecosystem. In an FO-MED scheme, the brine reject from the last
84 effect of the MED unit is used by a FO process as draw solution, which reduces the water
85 footprint and total saline water rejected to the sea and in turn reduces the pumping power
86 consumption and chemicals' use in the FO draw solution [9]. This hybridization allows to raise
87 the energy efficiency of the MED process (and thus to reduce the CO₂ emissions) by increasing
88 simultaneously the top brine temperature and the number of MED effects.

89 The scientific literature about the use of FO as a pretreatment of thermal desalination
90 processes is scarce, especially in the case of MED. Khanafer et al. [10] evaluated the use of FO
91 as pretreatment of the MSF desalination process experimentally by using tertiary treated
92 wastewater as feed solution. This scheme reduced the divalent ions concentration of the brine
93 rejection up to 43%. Thabit et al. [11] investigated the use of FO experimentally as a
94 pretreatment of the feedwater of an MSF plant to dilute the brine rejection and reduce scale
95 formation propensity. Results showed that increasing the brine temperature from 25 to 40 °C
96 increased the membrane flux and the draw solution dilution from 3% to 8.5%, respectively,
97 reducing the concentration of divalent ions in the MSF feedwater. In particular, the dilution of
98 SO₄²⁻ ions in the DS, responsible of the hard scale deposits, was of 2.9% for 25 °C and of 7.7%
99 for 40 °C. Altaee et al. [9] evaluated the integration of FO and MSF processes. A reduction of
100 23% in the concentration of the ions Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺ and SO₄²⁻ in the feedwater to the MSF was
101 observed for a FO recovery ratio (RR) of 32%. Within the same work, the performance of an
102 FO-MED system for different FO recovery ratios (16 – 32%) was also predicted, where the DS
103 was the rejected brine of the MED unit. The scaling tendency of the feedwater was estimated
104 with the Ryznar scale index (*RSI*), which raised from 4.6 (severe scaling) without FO

105 pretreatment to 5.5 (light scaling) with FO at a 16% of recovery ratio. In this paper, the MED
106 and FO models were simulated independently, with the MED model considered as a black box.
107 In addition, the FO models used did not account for the concentration polarization (external and
108 internal) and the reverse salt flux effect. In a later work, Altaee et al. [12] presented an
109 assessment of the FO-MED performance with elevated TBTs, using a simplified FO model.
110 Results showed that for a TBT of 85 °C and seawater salinity of 45,000 ppm, the distillate
111 production increased 1.8 times, and the *RSI* was 5 (light scaling zone) for a FO recovery of
112 40%. It was also found that lower recoveries of FO led to severe scaling.

113 To the authors' best knowledge, there are no papers in the literature performing a
114 comprehensive energy and exergy analysis of an FO-MED hybrid system at different boundary
115 conditions using detailed models of both components (MED and FO). The authors of this paper
116 have developed a simulation tool based on first principles for both the MED and FO units,
117 considering critical detrimental effects of the FO such as internal and external concentration
118 polarization and reverse salt flux. The models have been implemented and integrated using the
119 software environment Engineering Equation Solver [13]. The tool has been used to perform a
120 thorough assessment of the potential of FO as a pretreatment of MED to increase its thermal
121 efficiency and reduce the environmental impact of the saline water disposal to the sea. For that
122 purpose, the effect of key parameters of the MED plant such as the number of effects, heating
123 steam temperature, MED recovery ratio, brine salinity, and intake seawater salinity and
124 temperature in the system performance has been analyzed. The analysis includes the estimation
125 of the scale deposition on the thermal unit caused by the precipitation of metal ions on the heat
126 exchangers, using the Ryznar scale index.

127 **2 System description and modeling**

128 In this section, the multi-effect distillation and forward-osmosis models are firstly detailed.
129 After that, the integration of the FO in the MED together with the fundamental equations of the
130 exergy analysis is presented.

131 **2.1 Multi-effect distillation model**

132 The MED process consists of consecutive evaporation – condensation processes inside vessels
133 called effects (see Fig. 1). Seawater is sprayed on the external surface of the falling film
134 evaporators producing vapor by boiling due to the vaporization enthalpy released by the vapor
135 condensation inside the tubes. The vapor produced in one effect is the energy source of the next
136 evaporation process except for the first evaporator, where external saturated steam is needed.
137 The temperature of this heating steam is usually below 70 °C to avoid scaling issues. Part of
138 the vapor produced in each effect is used to preheat the feedwater in the preheaters after
139 removing the water droplets when passing through a demister. The condensed steam (distillate)
140 from the evaporators and preheaters is collected in flash boxes, producing additional vapor by
141 flashing the distillate. Besides, the extra vapor produced by flash is obtained when the resulting
142 unevaporated brine at the bottom of one effect goes to the following evaporator at lower
143 pressure. Finally, the vapor produced in the last effect is condensed in the end condenser, which
144 is cooled by the available cooling source (intake seawater in this case). The brine generated in
145 the process is generally rejected back to the sea causing an important environmental impact.

146

147

Fig. 1. Scheme of multi-effect distillation process for seawater desalination.

148

The MED configuration selected for this work is forward feed due to the lower risk of scaling

149

when increasing the operating temperature compared to other layouts. Based on mass and

150

energy balances and heat transfer equations, a mathematical design model was developed and

151

published by Ortega-Delgado et al. [14]. For the sake of brevity, only representative equations

152

are shown in Table 1. Such a model was validated with good agreement and permits to

153

determine the temperatures, pressures, mass flow rates of each process flow stream along with

154

the heat transfer areas of evaporators, preheaters, and the end condenser.

155

Table 1. Brief summary of MED model equations [14].

Comment	Equation	No.
Mass balance	$\dot{m}_{Bi} = \dot{m}_{B,i-1} - \dot{m}_{Di} - \dot{m}_{FEi}$	(1)
Salt balance	$\dot{m}_F X_F = \dot{m}_{Bi} X_i$	(2)
Energy balance	$(1 - \alpha_{i-1})\dot{m}_{T,i-1}\lambda_{c,i-1} + \dot{m}_{FB,i}h''_{Vi} + \dot{m}_{B,i-1}h_{B,i-1}$ $= (1 - \alpha_i)\dot{m}_{Ti}h'_{Vi} + \alpha_i\dot{m}_{Ti}h'_{ci}$ $+ \dot{m}_F\bar{c}_{p,preh,i}(T_{preh,i} - T_{preh,i+1}) + \dot{m}_{Bi}h_{Bi}$	(3)
Brine flashing	$\dot{m}_{FEi}\lambda_{FEi} = \dot{m}_{B,i-1}\bar{c}_{p,FEi}(T_{i-1} - T_{B,FEi})$	(4)
Distillate flashing	$\dot{m}_{C,i-1}h''_{c,i-1} + (1 - \alpha_{i-1})\dot{m}_{T,i-1}h_{c,i-1} + \alpha_i\dot{m}_{Ti}h'_{ci} = \dot{m}_{FB,i}h''_{Vi} + \dot{m}_{ci}h''_{ci}$	(5)
Heat transfer	$\dot{Q}_i = (1 - \alpha_{i-1})\dot{m}_{Ti}\lambda_{c,i-1} = A_i U_{ev,i}(T_{c,i-1} - T_i)$	(6)
Thermal losses	$T_{c,i} = T_{Vi} - BPE_i - (\Delta T_{m,i} + \Delta T_{l,i} + \Delta T_{c,i})$	(7)

156

157

There are two key parameters to evaluate the thermal efficiency and investment costs of the

158

MED plant: the specific thermal energy consumption and the specific heat transfer area,

159 respectively. The specific thermal energy consumption ($STEC$, kWh/m³) is determined by Eq.

160 (8):

$$STEC = \frac{\dot{m}_s \lambda_s}{\dot{m}_d / \rho_d} \cdot \frac{1}{3600} \quad (8)$$

161 where \dot{m}_s (kg/s) is the mass flow rate of heating steam, λ_s (kJ/kg) is the specific enthalpy of
162 condensation of the heating steam at a temperature T_s , \dot{m}_d (kg/s) is the mass flow rate of
163 distillate produced, and ρ_d (kg/m³) is the density of the distillate.

164 The specific heat transfer area, sA (m²·s/kg) is related to the area of the heat exchangers, and it
165 is determined as follows:

$$sA = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N A_{ev,i} + \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} A_{preh,i} + A_c}{\dot{m}_d} \quad (9)$$

166 where $A_{ev,i}$ (m²) is the surface area of the evaporator i , $A_{preh,i}$ (m²) is the surface area of the
167 preheater i , and A_c (m²) is the surface area of the end condenser.

168 The power consumption of the pumps (brine, distillate, and cooling) is also another important
169 parameter to be considered, which can be determined as follows:

$$\dot{W}_p = \frac{(p_d - p_s) \cdot \dot{V}}{\eta_p \cdot \eta_m} \quad (10)$$

170 where p_d (Pa) is the discharge pressure of the pump, p_s (Pa) is the suction pressure of the pump,
171 \dot{V} (m³/s) is the volumetric flow rate of the fluid going through the pump, η_p and η_m (-) are the
172 pump (considering mechanical and internal losses) and electric motor efficiencies, respectively.

173

174 **2.2 Forward osmosis model**

175 When two solutions with different salinities are put in contact by a semipermeable membrane,
176 the solvent tends to pass naturally from the less concentrated solution to the more concentrated
177 solution to balance the chemical potential (see Fig. 2). At the outlet of the membrane modules,

196 al. [18]. The model has been validated against experimental data and allows estimating the
 197 water flux, J_w , from the feed solution to the draw solution, with the support layer of the
 198 membrane facing the feed solution, which enhances the water flux across the membrane [19].
 199 It also takes into account the effect of reverse salt flux, internal and external concentration
 200 polarization. The osmotic pressures of the solutions are determined using the Pitzer semi-
 201 empirical equations [20] (Appendix A), which accounts for the deviation from the ideal
 202 behavior with the osmotic coefficient ϕ (Eqs. (14) and (15)). This is especially important when
 203 dealing with high salinity solutions like in our case. Note that most of the works published use
 204 the Van't Hoff equation to calculate the osmotic pressures, which is valid only for low
 205 concentration solutions. In addition, the FS and DS bulk concentrations (C_{Fb} and C_{Db} ,
 206 respectively) have been taken as the average value between the inlet and the outlet
 207 concentrations. For the sake of brevity, only key equations are presented in Table 2.

208 Table 2. Resume of main equations of the FO model.

Comment	Equation	No.
Bulk concentration of the DS	$C_{Db,x} = \left(\frac{C_{Di,x} + C_{Do,x}}{2} \right)$	(11)
Bulk concentration of the FS	$C_{Fb,x} = \left(\frac{C_{Fi,x} + C_{Fo,x}}{2} \right)$	(12)
Water flux	$J_{w,x} = A_w \left(\frac{\pi_{Db,x} \exp\left(\frac{-J_{w,x}}{k_D}\right) - \pi_{Fb,x} \exp\left(J_{w,x}K + \frac{J_{w,x}}{k_F}\right)}{1 + \frac{B}{J_{w,x}} \left(\exp\left(J_{w,x}K + \frac{J_{w,x}}{k_F}\right) - \exp\left(\frac{-J_{w,x}}{k_D}\right) \right)} \right)$	(13)
Bulk osmotic pressure of DS	$\pi_{Db,x} = \nu RT \phi_D C_{Db,x}$	(14)
Bulk osmotic pressure of FS	$\pi_{Fb,x} = \nu RT \phi_F C_{Fb,x}$	(15)

209

210 2.3 Integrated model

211 The models of the FO and MED have been integrated by considering the brine reject of the
 212 MED plant as the DS inlet of the FO membranes and the DS outlet as the feedwater of the MED
 213 unit (see Fig. 3). The FO membranes are located after the intake seawater system. The FS inlet

214 is raw seawater (intake seawater), which is also used as cooling water of the MED after passing
 215 through the FO membranes. The concentration of divalent ions in the feedwater of the MED
 216 plant is reduced with the FO pretreatment, thus minimizing the risk of scale formation in the
 217 heat exchangers' tubes. In addition, note that the permeate flow rate from the FS to the DS has
 218 to balance the feed flow rate of the MED; therefore, it must be equal to the distillate produced.

219

220

Fig. 3. Scheme of integrated FO-MED model.

221 The integrated model has been implemented in Engineering Equation Solver (EES) software
 222 environment [13]. This software is very flexible in performing sensitivity analyses that include
 223 multiple variables, requiring proper bounding and initialization for convergence. The input
 224 variables of the integrated model are: the number of MED effects (N), the distillate production
 225 (\dot{m}_d), the heating steam temperature (T_s), the recovery ratio of the MED (RR , ratio of the mass
 226 flow rate of distillate to the mass flow rate of feedwater), the ionic concentration and
 227 temperature of the intake seawater (X_{in}, T_{in}), the ionic concentration and temperature of the
 228 MED output brine (X_B, T_B), the differential temperature in the first preheater (DTT_{preh1}) and
 229 the temperature difference in the end condenser (ΔT_c). In addition, geometric parameters of the
 230 MED and FO systems have been considered for solving the model. The MED geometric
 231 parameters are the dimensions of the evaporators, effects, demisters and connecting lines and
 232 the FO membrane parameters are membrane width and length, water permeability coefficient,

233 salt diffusion coefficient, mass transfer coefficients, diffusivity, structure parameter and solute
234 resistivity.

235 There are two system parameters related to the amount of water produced with respect to the
236 total intake seawater (global recovery ratio, RR_g) and the total amount of intake water used in
237 the process (water footprint, WF), both accounting for the environmental impact of the
238 desalination process:

$$RR_g = \frac{\dot{m}_d}{\dot{m}_{intake}} \quad (16)$$

$$WF = \dot{m}_{intake} \quad (17)$$

239 **2.4 Exergy analysis**

240 The exergy analysis identifies and quantifies exergy destruction sources, providing insight into
241 how far this system is from its maximum potential. It also allows performing fair comparisons
242 between different interactions (work, heat, inputs, outputs) [21]. The exergy of a system in a
243 particular thermodynamic state can be defined as the maximum theoretical work obtainable
244 when the system acquires thermal, mechanical and chemical equilibrium with the environment,
245 and the heat transfer occurs with the environment only [22]. In the absence of nuclear, magnetic
246 and electrical interactions, two components of the exergy can be considered: thermomechanical
247 (pressure and temperature variation) and chemical (composition). The potential and kinetic
248 components have been neglected as the system has been considered stationary in reference to
249 the environment.

250 The thermomechanical exergy can be defined as the maximum theoretical useful work obtained
251 when the system reaches thermal and mechanical equilibrium with the environment at p_0 , T_0
252 while maintaining its original composition x_i (restricted dead state, denoted with an asterisk).
253 The chemical exergy is defined as the maximum theoretical useful work obtainable when the

254 system reaches chemical equilibrium with the environment, maintaining its pressure p_0 and
 255 temperature T_0 (global dead state). Therefore, the specific flow exergy e (J/kg) of a stream of
 256 matter is determined as follows:

$$e = e^{PH} + e^{CH} \quad (18)$$

$$e^{PH} = (h - h^*) - T_0(s - s^*)$$

$$e^{CH} = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i (\mu_i^* - \mu_i^0)$$

257 where h (J/kg) is the specific enthalpy, s (J/(kg·K)) is the specific entropy, T (K) is the
 258 temperature, x_i (-) is the mass fraction, and μ (J/kg) is the chemical potential of the component
 259 i . For electrolyte solutions, the chemical potential can be determined as follows [23]:

$$\mu_i = \mu_i^0 + RT \ln \left(\frac{a_i}{a_i^0} \right) \quad (19)$$

260 where R (J/(kg·K)) is the universal gas constant and a_i (-) is the activity of the component i of
 261 the solution. Considering a solution of a solvent (s) and a solute (B), the chemical potential of
 262 the solute B is defined as:

$$\mu_B = \mu_B^0 + \nu RT \ln \left(\frac{m_{\pm} \gamma_{\pm}}{m_{\pm}^0 \gamma_{\pm}^0} \right) \quad (20)$$

263 where ν (-) is the total number of ions, m_{\pm} (mol/kg) is the mean molality and γ_{\pm} (-) is the mean
 264 activity coefficient. The chemical potential of the solvent s in the solution can be obtained with
 265 the following equation:

$$\mu_s = \mu_s^0 + RT \ln \left(\frac{a_s}{a_s^0} \right) \quad (21)$$

266 The activity of the solvent a_s can be determined known the osmotic coefficient ϕ :

$$\phi = \frac{-1000 \cdot \ln(a_s)}{M_s \sum_k \nu_k m_k} \quad (22)$$

267 where M_s (g/mol) is the molar mass of the solvent and ν_k (-) is the number of moles of the
268 electrolyte k .

269 The equations used to determine the exergy fluxes rates on the different points of the plant are
270 reported hereafter. Note that for the exergy analysis, an aqueous sodium chloride solution model
271 has been assumed for the seawater [24]. The osmotic and activity coefficients of NaCl and water
272 have been determined using Pitzer's semi-empirical equations [20] (see Appendix A). Seawater
273 properties have been determined using the correlations provided by Sharqawy et al. (2010).
274 Regarding the dead state, equal conditions than the environment, $p^0=101,325$ Pa, $T^0=25$ °C,
275 $s^0=35.879$ g/kg has been selected to have zero exergy of the intake seawater stream, as
276 recommended by Sharqawy et al. (2011).

277 The exergy flux rate of a stream of matter can be determined through:

$$\dot{E}x = e \cdot \dot{m} \quad (23)$$

278 The external work exergy transfer rate is calculated as follows:

$$\dot{E}x_W = \dot{W} \quad (24)$$

279 The FO-MED system has been disaggregated into two main subsystems for the exergy analysis:
280 MED and FO. There are also three pumps needed to drive the intake seawater, the distillate and
281 the brine stream. A scheme of the system with the different matter and energy streams is
282 depicted in Fig. 4. Note that a minimum pumping power for the intake seawater is required at
283 the inlet of the FO unit.

284

285 Fig. 4. Scheme of the FO-MED hybrid system for the exergy analysis. HS= Heating Steam,
 286 CW=Cooling Water, D=distillate, W=water, dist=distillate, B=Brine, FS=Feed Solution,
 287 DS=Draw Solution.

288 The exergy balance applied to a control volume is defined as follows:

$$\sum \dot{E}x_{in} = \sum \dot{E}x_{out} + \dot{E}x_D \quad (25)$$

289 where $\sum \dot{E}x_{in}$ (W) is the sum of the exergy rates of the input streams (heat, work, mass),
 290 $\sum \dot{E}x_{out}$ (W) is the sum of the exergy rates of the output streams (heat, work, mass) and $\dot{E}x_D$
 291 (W) is the exergy destruction. Alternatively, the exergy balance can be expressed using the fuel-
 292 product method proposed by Kotas [27] and Tsatsaronis [28] among others. In the latter,
 293 *product* (P) can be defined as the material or energy stream (one or multiple) of interest for
 294 which the system/component has been designed, and *fuel* (F) as the resources needed to
 295 generate the desired product. The exergy balance, in this case, is expressed as follows:

$$\dot{E}x_F = \dot{E}x_P + \dot{E}x_D + \dot{E}x_L \quad (26)$$

296 The term $\dot{E}x_L$ represents the exergy loss of the system that is rejected to the environment
 297 without any further use.

298 The exergy balances applied to the MED unit, distillate pump, brine pump, FO unit, and intake
 299 pump are presented in Eqs. (27)-(31), respectively:

$$\dot{E}x_{HS,in} + \dot{E}x_F + \dot{E}x_{CW,in} = \dot{E}x_{HS,out} + \dot{E}x_W + \dot{E}x_B + \dot{E}x_{CW,out} + \dot{E}x_{D,MED} \quad (27)$$

$$\dot{E}x_W + \dot{E}x_{Wp,dist} = \dot{E}x_{dist} + \dot{E}x_{D,Wp,dist} \quad (28)$$

$$\dot{E}x_B + \dot{E}x_{Wp,brine} = \dot{E}x_{DS,in} + \dot{E}x_{D,Wp,brine} \quad (29)$$

$$\dot{E}x_{FS,in} + \dot{E}x_{DS,in} = \dot{E}x_{FS,out} + \dot{E}x_{DS,out} + \dot{E}x_{D,FO} \quad (30)$$

$$\dot{E}x_{intake} + \dot{E}x_{Wp,intake} = \dot{E}x_{FS,in} + \dot{E}x_{D,WP,intake} \quad (31)$$

300 The exergy balance applied to a control volume delimited by the global plant is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{E}x_{HS,in} + \dot{E}x_{intake} + \dot{E}x_{Wp,dist} + \dot{E}x_{Wp,brine} + \dot{E}x_{Wp,intake} \\ = \dot{E}x_{HS,out} + \dot{E}x_{dist} + \dot{E}x_{CW,out} + \dot{E}x_D \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

301 The Second Law efficiency (exergy efficiency) can be defined depending on the selection of
 302 fuel and product streams and the component's particular purpose. For the MED, the brine
 303 produced is not rejected back to the sea but used as the draw solution of the FO unit. Therefore,
 304 it is considered, together with the distillate, as a product of the MED. The fuel is defined as the
 305 external heat rate and pumping power consumed by the plant:

$$\eta_{X,MED} = \frac{\dot{E}x_P}{\dot{E}x_F} = \frac{\dot{E}x_{dist} + \dot{E}x_B - \dot{E}x_F}{(\dot{E}x_{HS,in} - \dot{E}x_{HS,out}) + \dot{E}x_{Wp}} \quad (33)$$

306 Note that for the standalone MED case (without FO pretreatment) the exergy efficiency is
 307 defined in the same way, but the exergy rate of the feedwater ($\dot{E}x_F$) is replaced by the exergy
 308 rate of the intake seawater ($\dot{E}x_{intake}$). In the case of the FO, the exergy efficiency can be defined
 309 considering it as a dissipative mixing unit [22,28], instead of a productive component of the
 310 desalination process:

$$\eta_{X,FO} = \frac{\dot{E}x_{FS,out} - \dot{E}x_{FS,in}}{\dot{E}x_{DS,in} + \dot{E}x_{FS,in}} \quad (34)$$

311 Different approaches to the FO exergy efficiency can be found in [29] and [30].
312 The exergy efficiency of the global FO-MED desalination system is defined as the ratio of the
313 exergy rate of the product (exergy increase between the outlet distillate and the intake seawater)
314 to the exergy rate of the fuel used to generate the product (external heat and total pumping
315 power):

$$\eta_{x,tot} = \frac{\dot{E}x_{dist} - \dot{E}x_{intake}}{(\dot{E}x_{HS,in} - \dot{E}x_{HS,out}) + \dot{E}x_{Wp}} \quad (35)$$

316 **3 METHODS**

317 The performance assessment of the MED process with FO pretreatment is examined through
318 an energy and exergy sensitivity analysis, which accounts both quantitatively and qualitatively
319 for the feasibility of the hybrid FO-MED system, and by comparison with the standalone MED
320 process. The thermal efficiency of the FO-MED system is evaluated in terms of thermal energy
321 consumption per cubic meter of water produced using the *STEC* parameter defined previously.

322 **3.1 Sensitivity analysis**

323 A sensitivity analysis has been carried out under different boundary conditions to study the
324 performance of the MED unit using FO as pretreatment. In particular, the *STEC* and *sA* of the
325 MED unit have been analyzed as a function of the MED recovery ratio, intake seawater salinity
326 and temperature, output brine salinity, heating steam temperature and the number of MED
327 effects. Besides, other key parameters of the integrated system, such as FO membrane area
328 (A_m), permeate flux, and pumping power consumption have been evaluated. In order to
329 compare the FO-MED hybrid system with the conventional standalone MED process, a MED
330 plant with the characteristics shown in Table 3 has been selected as a base case. Note that the
331 temperature of the last effect has been assumed to be 10 °C above the intake seawater

332 temperature for all the simulations. The pump and motor efficiencies have been established at
 333 0.7 and 0.9, respectively [31].

334 Table 3. Base case MED parameters

Variable	Value
Number of effects, -	8
Capacity, m ³ /d	100
Heating steam temperature, °C	65
Recovery ratio, -	30%
Intake seawater temperature, °C	25
Intake seawater salinity, ppm	35,879
Last effect temperature, °C	35
End condenser temp. difference, °C	7
Differential temp. 1 st preheater, °C	3

335
 336 The ionic composition of the intake seawater and MED brine (in the FO-MED scheme) is
 337 depicted in Table 4. In the case of the intake seawater, the standard seawater composition has
 338 been taken using the seawater library from the WAVE software environment [32]. For the case
 339 of brine, a total TDS of 57,163 ppm has been considered [33].

340 Table 4. Ionic composition of intake seawater and MED rejected brine

Ions	Concentration (ppm)	
	Intake	Brine
K ⁺	408.41	271.6
Na ⁺	11,033	20,353.3
Mg ²⁺	1314	907.5
Ca ²⁺	422	295.5
Cl ⁻	19,804	33,331.5
SO ₄ ²⁻	2776	1902

HCO ₃ ⁻	107	99.7
CO ₃ ²⁻	15	1.57
TDS	35,879	57,163

341

342 The variables and their range of variation selected are detailed in Table 5. For each analysis,
 343 one variable has been changed, and the rest maintained constant and equal to the base case,
 344 except in the case of analyzing the influence of the intake seawater salinity and the number of
 345 MED effects. In these cases, the brine salinity was increased from the reference value to make
 346 the osmotic pressure difference between DS and FS positive in each element of the discretized
 347 membrane, which would allow a positive permeate flux from FS to DS in all the variation range
 348 selected. In the case of the variation of the intake seawater salinity, the brine salinity was double
 349 of the reference one (i.e., 114,325 ppm). In the case of the variation of the number of effects,
 350 the brine salinity was set at 20% higher than the reference one (i.e., 68,595 ppm). Note that the
 351 concentration of all the ions were obtained by multiplying by the same increment factor in each
 352 case.

353

Table 5. Inputs variables varied in the sensitivity analysis

Variable	Range of variation
Number of effects	8 – 16
Heating steam temperature, °C	65 – 100
Recovery ratio, -	10 – 50%
Intake seawater temperature, °C	15 – 40
Intake seawater salinity, ppm	3588 – 71,759
Output brine salinity, ppm	57,163 – 114,325

354

355 An estimation of the alkaline scale deposits presented in the MED heat exchangers has been
 356 done using the Ryznar scale index (*RSI*) [34], defined as:

$$RSI = 2pHs - pH \quad (36)$$

357 where pHs is the pH value at saturation in calcium carbonate and pH is the water pH (which
 358 has been considered equal to 8.1 in this work). The term pHs is calculated with Eqs. (37) –
 359 (41):

$$pHs = (9.3 + A + B) - (C + D) \quad (37)$$

$$A = (\log_{10}(TDS) - 1)/10 \quad (38)$$

$$B = -13.12 \cdot \log_{10}(T + 273.15) + 34.55 \quad (39)$$

$$C = \log_{10}(Ca^{2+} \text{ mg/L as } CaCO_3) - 0.4 \quad (40)$$

$$D = \log_{10}(\text{Alk. mg/L as } CaCO_3) \quad (41)$$

360 where T ($^{\circ}C$) is the solution temperature. This index has been evaluated for the feedwater before
 361 being sprayed in the first effect (after passing through all preheaters). It will help identify
 362 unfeasible operation points because of the risk of scaling (see Table 6).

363 Table 6. Ryznar Scale Index

$RSI > 9$	Severe corrosion
$7.5 < RSI < 9$	Heavy corrosion
$7 < RSI < 7.5$	Significant corrosion
$6 < RSI < 7$	Stable water
$5 < RSI < 6$	Moderate to light scaling
$4 < RSI < 5$	Severe scaling

364

365 Table 7 shows the characteristics of the FO membrane selected [35–37].

366 Table 7. Characteristics of the FO membrane [35–37].

Variable	Value
Area per membrane element, m^2	24
Membrane width, m^2	1

Water permeability coeff. A_w , L/(m ² ·h·bar)	1.23
Salt permeability coeff. B , kg/(m ² ·h)	2.6
Membrane length L , m	1
Membrane width W , m	1
Draw-side mass transfer coeff. k_D , m/h	0.18
Feed-side mass transfer coeff. k_F , m/h	0.18
Structural parameter S , μm	230
Solute diffusion coefficient D , m ² /s	2.08·10 ⁻⁹
Solute resistivity K , h/m	S/D

367 4 RESULTS

368 4.1 Sensitivity analysis

369 The sensitivity analysis results, including the effect of the variation of the MED recovery ratio,
370 brine outlet concentration, intake seawater salinity and temperature, heating steam temperature
371 and the number of MED effects on the system performance, are presented hereafter.

372 4.1.1 Effect of the MED recovery ratio

373 The effect of the MED recovery ratio on the *STEC*, *RSI* and feedwater salinity is presented in
374 Fig. 5a. Note that the *RR* variation has an impact on the MED feedwater (DS outlet) salinity or
375 flow rate since both the brine (DS inlet) salinity and the plant capacity are fixed. When the *RR*
376 is increased from 10% to 50%, the *STEC* decreases from 112 to 90 kWh/m³ and the feedwater
377 salinity is also reduced from 51,441 to 28,581 ppm. This can be attributed to the consequent
378 decrease in the MED feedwater flow rate ($RR = \dot{m}_d/\dot{m}_F$), which causes a lower amount of
379 external steam needed to produce the same distillate flow rate. In addition, the *RSI* increases
380 with the *RR*, from 6.1 to 7, which means a decrease in the risk of scaling caused by the reduction
381 of feedwater salinity. However, recovery ratios higher than 30% are considered unfeasible

382 operating points as the DS outlet salinity becomes lower than the FS outlet salinity and there
 383 would not be a positive permeate flux through the FO membrane. This fact is reflected in Fig.
 384 5b (performed for a RR of 30%), which depicts the concentration profiles of FS and DS together
 385 with the permeate flux (Q_p) along the axis of the discretized membrane. As it can be seen, the
 386 permeate flux is higher in the first part of the membrane. It then decreases smoothly, while the
 387 DS outlet salinity and the FS outlet salinity get closer until being almost identical at
 388 40,000 ppm. Higher RR values would cause further reduction of the DS outlet salinity and a
 389 negative gradient of osmotic pressure from the DS to the FS, leading to a reverse permeate flux
 390 in the membrane. Fig. 5c shows the variation of the sA and A_m with the RR . The sA slightly
 391 decreases with the RR , while the A_m also has a moderate increase, from 629 m² to 1428 m².
 392 This can be explained by the reduction of flow rate and salinity of the DS at the outlet of the
 393 FO (feedwater to MED), which in turn reduces the required heat transfer areas to produce the
 394 given distillate and also reduce the osmotic pressure gradient, thus increasing the FO membrane
 395 area required. Fig. 5d depicts the exergy efficiency of the MED, FO, the overall system, and
 396 the pumping power. Given the definitions of section 2.4, the exergy efficiency of the MED
 397 increases slightly from 6.1% to 9.1% up to the maximum feasible value of the RR (30%),
 398 mainly due to the lower heating steam requirements associated with a lower feedwater salinity,
 399 which is linked to a decrease in the exergy destruction in the MED (Fig. 5e). The exergy
 400 efficiency of the FO also increases from 0.6% to 2.6% because of the reduction of the exergy
 401 input ($\dot{E}_{FS.in} + \dot{E}_{DS.in}$) and the increase of the exergy gained by the FS (see Fig. 5f). It can be
 402 seen that the exergy destruction of the MED is much higher than that of the FO (38,898 W vs.
 403 246 W respectively, at $RR=30\%$). Therefore, potentially, the MED efficiency could have a
 404 significant improvement by removing or diminishing its internal thermodynamic
 405 irreversibilities. Finally, the total exergy efficiency increases from 7.7 to 9.5% due to the lower

406 external heat and pumping requirements, which decreases from 4.7 ($RR=10\%$) to 2.2 kW
 407 ($RR=30\%$).

408 Fig. 5. Effect of the MED RR on (a) the $STEC$, RSI and s_F , (b) the DS and FS concentration
 409 profiles and permeate flux per element along the discretized membrane, (c) the sA and A_m ,
 410 (d) the exergy efficiency of the plant, MED and FO, and the pumping power (e) the exergy
 411 rates of the streams related to the MED, (f) the exergy rates of the streams related to the FO.

412 Reference case: $N=8$, $\dot{m}_d=100\text{ m}^3/\text{d}$, $T_s=65\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $X_B=57,163\text{ ppm}$, $X_{in}=35,879\text{ ppm}$.

413 4.1.2 Effect of the MED brine salinity

414 Fig. 6a shows the variation of the $STEC$ and RSI as a function of the brine salinity. The $STEC$
 415 is not practically affected by the brine salinity, whose impact is balanced by the heat transfer

416 areas of the evaporators. On the contrary, the risk of scaling increases with the brine salinity,
 417 as expected, passing the *RSI* from stable water (between 6 and 7) for 57.2 g/kg to light or
 418 moderate scaling (between 5 and 6) for 114.3 g/kg. The *sA* has a moderate increase as
 419 anticipated, from 346 to 411 m²/(kg/s), while the FO membrane area is reduced significantly,
 420 from 1428 to 225 m², due to the higher osmotic pressure difference (Fig. 6b). As mentioned
 421 previously, feasible points of the FO-MED operation require a concentration gradient from the
 422 DS to the FS. The increase of the brine salinity promotes this gradient and increases the
 423 permeate flux between FS and DS (Fig. 6c), passing from 2.9 L/(hm²) for a brine salinity of
 424 57.2 g/kg to 18.5 L/(hm²) for a brine salinity of 114.3 g/kg. The brine salinity does not have a
 425 significant influence on the global exergy efficiency (about 9.5%) due to the recirculation of
 426 the brine inside the system (Fig. 6d). The pumping power is not affected significantly by the
 427 increase of the brine salinity. The exergy efficiency of the MED increases with the brine salinity
 428 from 9.2% up to 21%, which can be attributed to the higher net exergy content of the product
 429 (distillate plus brine minus feed) while maintaining a similar value of the fuel streams (heating
 430 steam and pumps) (see Fig. 6e). On the contrary, the exergy efficiency of the FO unit decreases
 431 from 2.6% to 0.6% due to the increase of the fuel term (higher exergy content of the inlet DS
 432 stream) while the product term (exergy gained by the FS) is not affected (Fig. 6f). Note how
 433 the MED exergy destruction slightly decreases with the increase of the brine salinity, while the
 434 FO exergy destruction has the opposite tendency.

435 Fig. 6. Effect of the MED brine salinity on (a) the *STEC* and *RSI*, (b) the *sA* and *A_m*, and (c)
 436 the permeate flux (d) the exergy efficiency of the plant, MED, and FO, and the pumping
 437 power (e) the exergy rates of streams related to the MED, (f) the exergy rates of streams
 438 related to the FO. Reference case: $N=8$, $\dot{m}_d=100 \text{ m}^3/\text{d}$, $T_s=65 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $RR=30\%$, $X_{in}=35,879 \text{ ppm}$.

439 4.1.3 Effect of the intake seawater salinity and temperature

440 The effect of the intake seawater salinity on the FO membrane area and permeate flux is shown
 441 in Fig. 7a. The decrease of the intake seawater salinity from the reference value (35.9 g/kg) to
 442 3.6 g/kg (i.e., brackish water) leads to a higher osmotic pressure gradient in the FO membranes
 443 increasing the permeate flux from 18.5 to 47.5 L/(hm²). Moreover, it leads to a lower FO
 444 membrane area required, changing from 225 to 87 m². In contrast, the increase of the intake
 445 salinity from 35.9 g/kg ppm up to 71.8 g/kg leads to a decrease in the driving force of the
 446 process, which causes a lower permeate flux (4 L/(hm²) for 71.8 g/kg). In this case, the
 447 membrane area required increases up to 1044 m². The intake salinity does not affect the *STEC*
 448 of the MED and it has not been represented. The global exergy efficiency (Fig. 7b) increases
 449 with the intake salinity from 3% to 17.7% due to the higher exergy increase of the distillate

450 produced in comparison with that of the intake water (the fuel term does not change
 451 significantly), which is null. Note that the dead state conditions selected are equal to those of
 452 the intake seawater. The exergy efficiency of the FO takes almost null values up to around 35
 453 g/kg and then slowly increases, reaching a value of 5.3% for 71.8 g/kg, due to the decrease of
 454 the fuel term (Fig. 7c). The exergy efficiency of the MED does not change significantly (~21%),
 455 as well as the pumping power consumption (~2.2 kW), as it does not depend on the intake water
 456 salinity. In this case, the exergy content of the brine and feed decrease at about the same rate
 457 (Fig. 7d) as they approach the intake water salinity. Accordingly, no significant changes occur
 458 in the exergy destruction of the MED with the change in the intake seawater salinity, while in
 459 the FO, it slightly decreases.

460 Fig. 7. Effect of the intake seawater salinity on (a) the FO membrane area and permeate flux,
 461 (b) the exergy efficiency of MED, FO and global system, and the pumping power (c) the
 462 exergy rate of the streams relative to the FO, (d) the exergy rate of the streams relative to the
 463 MED. Reference case: $N=8$, $\dot{m}_d=100 \text{ m}^3/\text{d}$, $T_s=65 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $RR=30\%$, $X_B=114,325 \text{ ppm}$.

464

465 Regarding the intake seawater temperature variation, when it decreases from 25 °C to 15 °C
466 (Fig. 8a), a higher temperature difference between effects (ΔT_{eff} , driving force of the MED
467 process) is obtained, passing from 3.3 to 4.6 °C. It affects the required sA that is reduced from
468 346 to 274 $m^2/(kg/s)$. In contrast, higher intake seawater temperatures lead to a lower
469 temperature difference between effects in the MED unit and higher heat transfer area is needed.
470 In particular, increasing the intake seawater temperature from 25 °C to 40 °C results in a ΔT_{eff}
471 of 1.4 °C and sA of 725 $m^2/(kg/s)$. The effect on the $STEC$ and permeate flux is shown in Fig.
472 8b, where it can be seen that the $STEC$ is slightly reduced when the intake seawater temperature
473 increases. In particular, increasing T_{intake} from 15 to 40 °C leads to a reduction of the $STEC$
474 from 95.5 to 90.4 kWh/m^3 . This trend can be explained by the higher feedwater temperature at
475 the inlet of the MED first effect (the higher the intake seawater temperature, the higher the
476 feedwater temperature at the outlet of the preheaters of the MED unit). Also, the permeate flow
477 rate is slightly reduced from 2.9 to 2.8 Lh/m^2 , which can be attributed to the lower flow rate of
478 the FS because of the lower intake seawater flow rate needed at the end condenser when
479 increasing the intake seawater temperature. The global exergy efficiency increases with the
480 intake temperature (Fig. 8c) from 7.7% to 15.2%, with a similar trend of the MED exergy
481 efficiency (7.3% to 15%). This is due to the reduction of the irreversibilities associated with the
482 temperature drop in the MED. The lower the temperature difference in the effects, the smaller
483 exergy destruction (Fig. 8d). In addition, the waste heat requirements are lower and the exergy
484 used from the external steam decreases. The exergy efficiency of the FO does not change
485 significantly, increasing slightly between 2.5% and 2.8%, similarly as the pumping power
486 consumption.

487 Fig. 8. Effect of intake seawater temperature on (a) the sA and ΔT_{eff} (b) the $STEC$ and
 488 permeate flux (c) the exergy efficiency of MED, FO and global plant, and the power
 489 pumping consumption (d) the exergy rate of the streams related to the MED. Reference case:
 490 $N=8$, $\dot{m}_d=100\ m^3/d$, $T_s=65\ ^{\circ}C$, $RR=30\%$, $X_B=57,163\ ppm$ and $X_{in}=35,879\ ppm$.
 491

492 4.1.4 Effect of the heating steam temperature

493 The effect of the increase of the heating steam, or equivalently the top brine temperature, from
 494 $65\ ^{\circ}C$ to $100\ ^{\circ}C$ has hardly influence on the $STEC$ of the MED unit (it goes from 93.6 to 95.2
 495 kWh/m^3), as seen in Fig. 9a. What raises the performance of the MED unit is the increase in the
 496 number of effects since higher reuse of the vapor is given to produce freshwater. On the other
 497 hand, the increase in the heating steam affects the RSI that is reduced from 6.5 (stable water)
 498 to 5.6 (light scaling). Regarding the specific heat transfer area of the MED (as seen in Fig. 9b),
 499 it is reduced importantly from 346 to $190\ m^2/(kg/s)$ due to the rise of the temperature difference
 500 between effects of the MED unit from 3.3 to $7.6\ ^{\circ}C$. The heating steam temperature has no
 501 relevant effect on the FO membrane area and the permeate flux; therefore, they have not been

502 represented. The exergy efficiency of the plant and the MED unit decreased from 9.5% to 5.9%
 503 and from 9.2% to 5.6%, respectively, with the increase of the heating steam temperature
 504 between 65 °C and 100 °C (Fig. 9c) because of the abovementioned reasons in the analysis of
 505 the intake seawater temperature variation. Higher temperature differences between effects lead
 506 to higher exergy destruction rates, and consequently, the heating steam requirements are greater
 507 (see Fig. 9d). The performance of the FO unit and the pumping power consumption are not
 508 affected appreciably by the heating steam temperature variation.

509 Fig. 9. Effect of the heating steam temperature on (a) the $STEC$ and RSI (b) the sA and ΔT_{eff} ,

510 (c) the exergy efficiency of the MED, FO and global plant, and the pumping power

511 consumption, and (d) exergy rates of the streams related to the MED unit. Reference case:

512 $N=8$, $\dot{m}_d=100 \text{ m}^3/\text{d}$, $RR=30\%$, $X_B=57,163 \text{ ppm}$, $X_{in}=35,879 \text{ ppm}$.

513

514 4.1.5 *Effect of the simultaneous increase of MED number of effects and heating steam*
515 *temperature*

516 As mentioned before, the increase of the performance of the MED unit cannot be achieved by
517 only increasing the heating steam temperature, but an increase in the number of effects is also
518 required. Therefore, a simultaneous increase of both variables is performed in this section. The
519 increase in the number of effects leads to a decrease in the cooling requirements due to the
520 lower amount of vapor produced in the last effect. This reduces the FS flow rate -, and increases
521 the solution concentration at the FO membrane outlet. It can lead to a negative osmotic pressure
522 difference with the DS at the last part of the membrane. To avoid this, in this analysis, as it has
523 been anticipated, the brine salinity has been slightly increased (20%) with respect to the
524 reference value (57,163 ppm) so that there is always a positive osmotic pressure difference.

525 Fig. 10a shows the trend of the *STEC* and the *sA* for an increase in the MED number of effects
526 from 8 to 16, considering four different heating steam temperatures (65, 80, 90, and 100 °C).
527 As can be seen, for all the temperatures, the *STEC* decreases significantly from 94 to
528 53 kWh/m³, but the specific heat transfer area increases, having a minimum of 192.8 m²/(kg/s)
529 for 8 effects and 100 °C and reaching a maximum of 765 m²/(kg/s) for 16 effects and 65 °C.
530 Thus, a compromise solution between efficiency and capital costs should be considered to
531 decide the best design. Regarding the *RSI* (Fig. 10b), it only changes with the heating steam
532 temperature, but it is not affected by the number of MED effects (all the curves are overlapped).
533 The scale risk increases with the temperature and it becomes severe above 100 °C
534 approximately (*RSI* of 5.1). Light/moderate scaling may occur between 65 and 100 °C under
535 the conditions examined (passing from 6.2 to 5.1, respectively). The effect of the variation of
536 *N* on the temperature difference between effects is also shown in Fig. 10b, for different heating
537 steam temperatures. The simultaneous increase of *N* and *T_s* from 8 effects and 65 °C to 16

538 effects and 100 °C can maintain an approximately equal $\Delta T_{eff,av}$ (3.2 vs 3.4 °C), still avoiding
539 a severe scale scenario (passing the *RSI* from 6.2 to 5.1) but with a huge decrease in the *STEC*
540 (a reduction of approximately 50%, from 93.5 to 53.5 kWh/m³). The global exergy efficiency
541 increases with the number of effects and with the decrease in the heating steam temperatures
542 (see Fig. 10c). The maximum exergy efficiency (16.4%) is reached for $N=16$ effects and
543 $T_s=65$ °C. Note that the best operating point from a cost-benefit perspective (16 effects and 100
544 °C, minimum *sA*) does not correspond with the point of maximum exergy efficiency. This
545 system could operate closer to a reversible process and therefore make better use of the external
546 heat rate with $T_s=65$ °C, but at the expense of increasing the capital cost associated with higher
547 heat transfer areas in the heat exchangers. Another benefit of this operation point with
548 maximum exergy efficiency is the higher *RSI* (6.1), further reducing the risk of scaling. The
549 pumping power consumption decreases from 2.2 to 1.7 kW when the number of MED effects
550 is increased from 8 to 16, but it is not affected by the heating steam temperature. The increase
551 of exergy efficiency of the plant is due to the increase of the exergy efficiency in the MED
552 (19.5% for 16 effects and 65 °C), while the FO unit is not affected by the variation of the heating
553 steam temperature and increases linearly from 1.8% to 4.6% with the number of MED effects
554 (Fig. 10d). Increasing the number of MED effects reduces the external steam consumption
555 while higher steam temperatures lead to higher temperature differences between effects and
556 higher exergy destruction.

557

558 Fig. 10. Effect of the number of MED effects (N) and heating steam temperature (T_s) on (a)
 559 the $STEC$ and sA , (b) the RSI and ΔT_{eff} , (c) the global exergy efficiency and pumping power,
 560 and (d) the MED and FO exergy efficiencies. $\dot{m}_d=100 \text{ m}^3/\text{d}$, $RR=30\%$, $X_B=68,595 \text{ ppm}$,
 561 $X_{in}=35,879 \text{ ppm}$.
 562

563 4.2 Comparison of the base case (standalone MED) and MED-FO

564 A comparison between the base case (standalone MED) and the hybrid system (MED with FO
 565 pretreatment) has been performed to show the benefits of this hybridization. For that purpose,
 566 the best FO-MED design in terms of sA and $STEC$ obtained in the previous section ($T_s = 100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$
 567 and 16 effects) has been considered for the comparison (see Appendix B). The standalone MED
 568 case has been simulated by removing the FO pretreatment and thus taking part of the intake
 569 seawater as cooling water and the rest as the feedwater to the MED. The results are shown in
 570 Table 8 and Table 9. It can be seen (Table 8) that the use of FO as a pretreatment of the MED
 571 feedwater to reduce the divalent ions permits to increase the heating steam temperature from

572 conventional 65 °C up to 100 °C and thus the number of MED effects from 8 to 16, reducing
573 the specific thermal energy consumption up to 50% (from 96 to 53.5 kWh/m³). It is achieved
574 with an 8.1% decrease of the specific heat transfer area of the MED unit (338.8 m²·s/kg in the
575 standalone MED and 311.3 m²·s/kg for FO-MED). Note that the pumping power consumption
576 is also reduced from 2.14 kW in the standalone MED to 1.74 kW in the FO-MED due to the
577 less total saline water rejected to the sea. In the standalone MED case, the volumetric flow rate
578 of brine and cooling water discharged are 9.3 m³/h and 30.3 m³/h, at 51.3 g/l and 35.9 g/l,
579 respectively, while in the case of FO-MED only the cooling water at the outlet of the FO is
580 discharge to the sea, being the volumetric flow rate 23 m³/h with a salinity of 42.2 g/l. The
581 global recovery ratio, defined as the ratio of fresh water mass flow rate to the intake seawater
582 mass flow rate, is higher for the FO-MED system (15%), with less water footprint (27.7 m³/h)
583 than in the case of standalone MED (9.2% and 43.6 m³/h, respectively). In addition, the risk of
584 scaling would be maintained in the range of light/moderate scale (*RSI* of 5.4 for standalone
585 MED and 5.1 for FO-MED). The exergy efficiency decreases from 14% of the standalone MED
586 to 10% of the FO-MED case because of the higher temperature of the heating steam in the latter
587 (100 °C).

588 Regarding the FO membrane area, considering 24 m² per membrane element, results in 708 m²
589 of area required, equivalent to 30 FO membrane elements approximately. Table 9 shows how
590 the FO pretreatment reduces the divalent ion concentrations of the feedwater compared to the
591 standalone MED case. In particular, the concentrations of Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, and SO₄²⁻ decreased from
592 422, 1314, and 2776 ppm to 248, 762, and 1598 ppm, which mean a reduction of 41.2%, 42%, and
593 42.4%, respectively.

594 Table 8. Comparison between the standalone MED and hybrid FO-MED system. Input
595 variables not shown here are equal to the MED reference case.

Variable	MED	FO-MED
Number of effects	8	16
Capacity, m ³ /d	100	100
Heating steam temperature	65	100
MED recovery ratio	30%	30%
Global recovery ratio, RR_g	9.2%	14.9%
MED feedwater salinity, ppm	35,879	48,017
Brine salinity, ppm	51,256	68,595
Water footprint, WF , m ³ /h	43.6	27.7
<i>Results</i>		
$STEC$, kWh/m ³	96	53.5
Pumping power, kW	2.14	1.74
Brine rejected to the sea, m ³ /h	9.3	-
Salinity of brine rejected, ppm	51,256	-
Cooling water rejected, m ³ /h	30.3	23
Salinity of cooling water rejected, ppm	35,879	42,177
η_x	14%	10%
sA , m ² ·s/kg	338.8	311.3
A_m , m ²	-	707.5
$\Delta T_{eff,av}$, °C	3.3	3.4
RSI , -	5.4	5.1

596

597 Table 9. MED feedwater ion composition comparison between standalone MED and MED-
598 FO.

Ions	Concentration (ppm)	
	Feed MED	Feed MED-FO
K ⁺	408.41	228
Na ⁺	11,033	17,097
Mg ²⁺	1314	762.3

Ca ²⁺	422	248.2
Cl ⁻	19,804	27,998
SO ₄ ²⁻	2776	1598
HCO ₃ ⁻	107	88
CO ₃ ²⁻	15	1.3
TDS	35,879	48,017

599 5 CONCLUSIONS

600 In this work, the potential of forward osmosis as a pretreatment to increase the thermal
601 efficiency of the multi-effect distillation process and to reduce the brine disposal environmental
602 impact has been investigated. A detailed energy and exergy sensitivity analysis has been carried
603 out to evaluate the improvement of the process efficiency without the risk of scaling by reducing
604 the divalent ions concentration of the MED feedwater. In addition, the reduction of saline water
605 rejected to the sea has been quantified. To that end, a simulation tool of the integrated system
606 considering comprehensive mathematical models of both FO and MED systems has been
607 developed. This tool allows performing a plant design (number of MED effects, heat transfer
608 areas, operating temperature, recovery ratio, FO membrane area, number of FO membrane
609 modules, etc.), taking into account feasible operation points that do not lead to scaling issues.

610 The sensitivity analysis revealed that increasing the MED recovery ratio reduces the specific
611 thermal energy consumption but is limited by the salinity of the intake seawater, i.e., FO
612 feedwater. Higher recoveries can lead to higher exergy efficiency and a negative osmotic
613 pressure gradient with reverse water flux in the FO membranes. The low salinity of the intake
614 seawater reduces the exergy efficiency but enhances the osmotic pressure gradient in the
615 membranes and thus the water permeation. In contrast, low intake seawater temperature
616 increases the available temperature difference in the MED and the exergy destruction, reducing
617 the specific heat transfer area required. The exergy analysis permitted to identify the MED as

618 the component with the highest exergy destruction, being comparatively much higher than that
619 of the FO. The increase of the intake seawater temperature and the decrease of the heating steam
620 temperature lead to a reduction of the MED exergy destruction, which is also reduced with the
621 increase of the number of MED effects.

622 It has been found that a simultaneous increase of the heating steam temperature and the number
623 of MED effects (from 65 °C and 8 effects to 100 °C and 16 effects) in the FO-MED hybrid
624 system reduces the specific thermal energy consumption by 50% (from 96 to 53 kWh/m³) and
625 the pumping power consumption by 18.7% with respect the conventional MED process. Also,
626 it has been proved the reduction of the specific heat transfer area by 8% without a higher risk
627 of scaling while maintaining a similar temperature difference between effects. Besides, a
628 reduction of about 42% is achieved in the concentration of divalent ions in the MED feedwater
629 by the FO pretreatment. It has been identified also an increase of the global recovery ratio that
630 also translates into a reduction by 42% in the volume of saline water rejected into the
631 environment and a reduction of the water footprint by 38%, lowering the environmental impact
632 of the desalination process. The sensitivity analysis revealed a trade-off between the operating
633 point with maximum energy efficiency (minimum specific thermal energy consumption) and
634 the point with maximum exergy efficiency (16.4%), which resulted in the highest specific heat
635 transfer area of the evaporators and thus the highest capital costs associated.

636 **ACKNOWLEDGMENTS**

637 This work has been carried out within the framework of the European project EERES4WATER
638 (Promoting energy-water nexus resource efficiency through renewable energy and energy
639 efficiency, EAPA 1058/2018). This project is co-financed by the Interreg Atlantic Area
640 Programme through the European Regional Development Fund.

641 This research was also made possible by the NPRP award (NPRP10-0117-170176) from Qatar
642 National Research Fund (QNRF).

643 **NOMENCLATURE**

644 *Symbols*

645	A	Area, m^2
646	a	Activity, -
647	A_w	Water permeability coefficient, $m^3/(m^2 \cdot h \cdot \text{bar})$
648	B	Salt permeability coefficient, $m^3/(m^2 \cdot h)$, or solute
649	BPE	Boiling Point Elevation, $^{\circ}C$
650	C	Concentration, mol/L
651	c_p	Specific heat at constant pressure, $J/(kg \cdot K)$
652	D	Solute diffusion coefficient, m^2/h
653	$\dot{E}x$	Exergy rate, W
654	e	Specific flow exergy, J/kg
655	h	Specific enthalpy, J/kg
656	J_w	Water flux, $m^3/(m^2 \cdot h)$
657	J_s	Salt flux, $m^3/(m^2 \cdot h)$
658	k	Mass transfer coefficient, m/h
659	K	Solute resistivity, h/m
660	\dot{m}	Mass flow rate, kg/s
661	M	Molar mass, g/mol
662	m_{\pm}	Mean molality, mol/kg
663	\dot{Q}	Rate of heat transfer, W
664	Q	Volumetric flux, $L/(h \cdot m^2)$
665	RSI	Ryznar scale index
666	R	Universal gas constant, $8.314 J/(mol \cdot K)$
667	RR	Recovery ratio
668	s	Specific entropy, $J/(kg \cdot K)$, or solvent
669	$STEC$	Specific thermal energy consumption, kWh/m^3

670	sA	Specific heat transfer area, $m^2/(kg \cdot s)$
671	S	Structural parameter of the support layer, m
672	T	Temperature, K or $^{\circ}C$
673	U	Overall heat transfer coefficient, $W/(m^2 \cdot K)$
674	\dot{V}	Volumetric flow rate, m^3/s
675	x	Mass fraction
676	X	Salinity, ppm

677 *Subscripts/superscripts*

678	0	<i>Dead state conditions</i>
679	$*$	<i>Restricted dead state</i>
680	av	Average
681	B	Brine
682	b	Bulk
683	CH	Chemical
684	c	Condenser or condensate
685	D	Draw or distillate
686	$dist$	Distillate
687	e	Element
688	eff	Effective
689	ev	Evaporator
690	F	Feed
691	FE	Flash vapor in the MED effect
692	FB	Flash vapor in the flashing box
693	HS	Heating steam
694	i	Inlet
695	l	Connecting lines
696	m	Demister
697	o	Outlet
698	PH	Physical
699	p	Permeate
700	$preh$	Preheater

701	s	Steam or salt
702	T	Total
703	V	Vapor
704	w	Water
705	x	Axial distance
706	'	Vapor conditions after demister
707	"	Vapor conditions in the flash box
708	<i>Acronyms/abbreviations</i>	
709	CECP	Concentrative External Concentration Polarization
710	CICP	Concentrative Internal Concentration Polarization
711	DS	Draw Solution
712	FO	Forward-Osmosis
713	FS	Feed Solution
714	MED	Multi-Effect Distillation
715	MSF	Multi-Stage Flash
716	NF	Nanofiltration
717	TBT	Top Brine Temperature
718	ZLD	Zero Liquid Discharge
719	<i>Greek letters</i>	
720	α	Mass fraction of steam condensed in the preheater
721	λ	Specific enthalpy of evaporation/condensation, J/kg
722	ν	Number of ions
723	γ_{\pm}	Mean activity coefficient
724	η_x	Exergy efficiency
725	μ	Chemical potential, J/kg
726	π	Osmotic pressure, bar
727	ρ	Density, kg/m ³
728	ϕ	Osmotic coefficient, -
729		

730 **REFERENCES**

- 731 [1] United Nations, The United Nations World Water Development Report 2021: Valuing
732 Water, Paris, 2021.
- 733 [2] Global Water Intelligence, IDA Desalination & Reuse Handbook 2021–2022, 2021.
- 734 [3] J. Schallenberg-Rodríguez, B. Del Rio-Gamero, N. Melian-Martel, T. Lis Alecio, J.
735 González Herrera, Energy supply of a large size desalination plant using wave energy.
736 Practical case: North of Gran Canaria, *Appl. Energy.* 278 (2020).
737 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2020.115681>.
- 738 [4] A.M. Hassan, M.A.K. Al-Sofi, A.S. Al-Amoudi, A.T.M. Jamaluddin, A.M. Farooque,
739 A. Rowaili, A.G.I. Dalvi, N.M. Kither, G.M. Mustafa, I.A.R. Al-Tisan, A new approach
740 to membrane and thermal seawater desalination processes using nanofiltration
741 membranes (Part 1), *Desalination.* 118 (1998) 35–51. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0011-](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0011-9164(98)00079-4)
742 [9164\(98\)00079-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0011-9164(98)00079-4).
- 743 [5] O.A. Hamed, Overview of hybrid desalination systems - Current status and future
744 prospects, *Desalination.* 186 (2005) 207–214.
745 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2005.03.095>.
- 746 [6] T. Altmann, J. Robert, A. Bouma, J. Swaminathan, J.H. Lienhard, Primary energy and
747 exergy of desalination technologies in a power-water cogeneration scheme, *Appl.*
748 *Energy.* 252 (2019) 113319. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2019.113319>.
- 749 [7] A.M. Hassan, Review of development of the new NF-seawater desalination process from
750 pilot plant to commercial production plant stages 1, 6th Saudi Eng. Conf. (2002).
- 751 [8] K. Touati, H.S. Usman, C.N. Mulligan, M.S. Rahaman, Energetic and economic
752 feasibility of a combined membrane-based process for sustainable water and energy
753 systems, *Appl. Energy.* 264 (2020) 114699.

- 754 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2020.114699>.
- 755 [9] A. Altaee, A. Mabrouk, K. Bourouni, A novel Forward osmosis membrane pretreatment
756 of seawater for thermal desalination processes, *Desalination*. 326 (2013) 19–29.
757 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2013.07.008>.
- 758 [10] D. Khanafer, I. Ibrahim, S. Yadav, A. Altaee, A. Hawari, J. Zhou, Brine reject dilution
759 with treated wastewater for indirect desalination, *J. Clean. Prod.* 322 (2021) 129129.
760 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JCLEPRO.2021.129129>.
- 761 [11] M.S. Thabit, A.H. Hawari, M.H. Ammar, S. Zaidi, G. Zaragoza, A. Altaee, Evaluation
762 of forward osmosis as a pretreatment process for multi stage flash seawater desalination,
763 *Desalination*. 461 (2019) 22–29. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2019.03.015>.
- 764 [12] A. Altaee, A. Mabrouk, K. Bourouni, P. Palenzuela, Forward osmosis pretreatment of
765 seawater to thermal desalination: High temperature FO-MSF/MED hybrid system,
766 *Desalination*. 339 (2014) 18–25. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2014.02.006>.
- 767 [13] S. Klein, *Engineering Equation Solver Software (EES)*, (2021).
768 <https://fchartsoftware.com/ees>.
- 769 [14] B. Ortega-Delgado, L. García-Rodríguez, D.C. Alarcón-Padilla, Opportunities of
770 improvement of the MED seawater desalination process by pretreatments allowing high-
771 temperature operation, *Desalin. Water Treat.* 97 (2017) 94–108.
772 <https://doi.org/10.5004/dwt.2017.21679>.
- 773 [15] J. Wang, X. Liu, Forward osmosis technology for water treatment: Recent advances and
774 future perspectives, *J. Clean. Prod.* 280 (2021) 124354.
775 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JCLEPRO.2020.124354>.
- 776 [16] A. Altaee, J. Zhou, A. Alhathal Alanezi, G. Zaragoza, Pressure retarded osmosis process
777 for power generation: Feasibility, energy balance and controlling parameters, *Appl.*
778 *Energy*. 206 (2017) 303–311. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2017.08.195>.

- 779 [17] A. Altaee, A. Braytee, G.J. Millar, O. Naji, Energy efficiency of hollow fibre membrane
780 module in the forward osmosis seawater desalination process, *J. Memb. Sci.* 587 (2019)
781 117165. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2019.06.005>.
- 782 [18] S.M. Ali, S.J. Im, A. Jang, S. Phuntsho, H.K. Shon, Forward osmosis system design and
783 optimization using a commercial cellulose triacetate hollow fibre membrane module for
784 energy efficient desalination, *Desalination*. 510 (2021) 115075.
785 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.DESAL.2021.115075>.
- 786 [19] B.S. Chanukya, S. Patil, N.K. Rastogi, Influence of concentration polarization on flux
787 behavior in forward osmosis during desalination using ammonium bicarbonate,
788 *Desalination*. 312 (2013) 39–44. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.DESAL.2012.05.018>.
- 789 [20] K.S. Pitzer, J.C. Peiper, R.H. Busey, Thermodynamic Properties of Aqueous Sodium
790 Chloride Solutions, *J. Phys. Chem. Ref. Data*. (1984). <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.555709>.
- 791 [21] A. Bejan, Fundamentals of exergy analysis, entropy generation minimization, and the
792 generation of flow architecture, *Int. J. Energy Res.* 26 (2002) 0–43.
793 <https://doi.org/10.1002/ER.804>.
- 794 [22] A. Bejan, G. Tsatsaronis, M.J. Moran, Thermal Design and Optimization, John Wiley
795 and Sons, New York etc., 1996.
- 796 [23] K.S. Pitzer, Activity Coefficients in Electrolyte Solutions, CRC Press, Boca Raton, 1991.
797 <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781351069472>.
- 798 [24] L. Fitzsimons, B. Corcoran, P. Young, G. Foley, Exergy analysis of water purification
799 and desalination: A study of exergy model approaches, *Desalination*. 359 (2015) 212–
800 224. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2014.12.033>.
- 801 [25] M.H. Sharqawy, J.H. Lienhard V, S.M. Zubair, Thermophysical properties of seawater:
802 A review of existing correlations and data, *Desalin. Water Treat.* 16 (2010) 354–380.
803 <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.5004/dwt.2010.1079>.

- 804 [26] M.H. Sharqawy, S.M. Zubair, J.H. Lienhard, Second law analysis of reverse osmosis
805 desalination plants: An alternative design using pressure retarded osmosis, *Energy*. 36
806 (2011) 6617–6626. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENERGY.2011.08.056>.
- 807 [27] T.J. Kotas, *The Exergy Method of Thermal Plant Analysis*, Elsevier, 1985.
808 <https://doi.org/10.1016/c2013-0-00894-8>.
- 809 [28] G. Tsatsaronis, Thermo-economic analysis and optimization of energy systems, *Prog.*
810 *Energy Combust. Sci.* 19 (1993) 227–257. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0360-1285\(93\)90016-](https://doi.org/10.1016/0360-1285(93)90016-8)
811 8.
- 812 [29] E.W. Tow, R.K. McGovern, J.H. Lienhard V, Raising forward osmosis brine
813 concentration efficiency through flow rate optimization, *Desalination*. 366 (2015) 71–
814 79. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.DESAL.2014.10.034>.
- 815 [30] K.H. Mistry, J.H. Lienhard, Generalized Least Energy of Separation for Desalination
816 and Other Chemical Separation Processes, *Entropy* 2013, Vol. 15, Pages 2046-2080. 15
817 (2013) 2046–2080. <https://doi.org/10.3390/E15062046>.
- 818 [31] B. Rahimi, A. Christ, K. Regenauer-Lieb, H.T. Chua, A novel process for low grade heat
819 driven desalination, *Desalination*. 351 (2014) 202–212.
820 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.DESAL.2014.07.021>.
- 821 [32] WAVE Software for Water Treatment Plant Design, (n.d.).
822 <https://www.dupont.com/water/resources/design-software.html> (accessed May 4, 2021).
- 823 [33] A. Altaee, Personal communication, (2021).
- 824 [34] F. García-Ávila, L. Ramos-Fernández, D. Pauta, D. Quezada, Evaluation of water quality
825 and stability in the drinking water distribution network in the Azogues city, Ecuador,
826 *Data Br.* 18 (2018) 111–123. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.DIB.2018.03.007>.
- 827 [35] A. Altaee, A. Cippolina, Modelling and optimization of modular system for power
828 generation from a salinity gradient, *Renew. Energy*. 141 (2019) 139–147.

829 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2019.03.138>.

830 [36] A. Altaee, N. AlZainati, Novel Thermal Desalination Brine Reject-Sewage Effluent
831 Salinity Gradient for Power Generation and Dilution of Brine Reject, *Energies* 2020,
832 Vol. 13, Page 1756. 13 (2020) 1756. <https://doi.org/10.3390/EN13071756>.

833 [37] W. Luo, M. Xie, X. Song, W. Guo, H.H. Ngo, J.L. Zhou, L.D. Nghiem, Biomimetic
834 aquaporin membranes for osmotic membrane bioreactors: Membrane performance and
835 contaminant removal, *Bioresour. Technol.* 249 (2018) 62–68.
836 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.BIORTECH.2017.09.170>.

837

838 **Appendix A**

839 **A.1 Osmotic and activity coefficients**

840 The mean activity coefficient γ (-) and the osmotic coefficient ϕ (-) of the NaCl aqueous
 841 solution have been calculated with the model of Pitzer et al. (1984), using Eqs. (A.1) and (A.2),
 842 respectively:

$$\ln\gamma = -|z_M z_X| A_\phi \left(\frac{I^{0.5}}{1 + bI^{0.5}} + \frac{2}{b} \ln(1 + bI^{0.5}) \right) + 2m \frac{\nu_M \nu_X}{\nu} \cdot \left\{ 2\beta_{MX}^{(0)} + \frac{2\beta_{MX}^{(1)}}{\alpha^2 I} \left[1 - \left(1 + \alpha I^{0.5} - \frac{\alpha^2 I}{2} \right) \cdot \exp(-\alpha I^{0.5}) \right] \right\} + 3m^2 \frac{(\nu_M \nu_X)^{3/2}}{\nu} C_{MX}^\phi \quad (\text{A.1})$$

$$\phi - 1 = -|z_M z_X| A_\phi \frac{I^{0.5}}{1 + bI^{0.5}} + m \frac{2\nu_M \nu_X}{\nu} \left[\beta_{MX}^{(0)} + \beta_{MX}^{(1)} \exp(-\alpha I^{0.5}) \right] + 2m^2 \frac{(\nu_M \nu_X)^{3/2}}{\nu} C_{MX}^\phi \quad (\text{A.2})$$

843 where z_M and z_X are the charge of the cation and anion, respectively, A_ϕ (kg/mol)^{0.5} is the
 844 Debye-Hückel parameter for the osmotic coefficient, I (mol/kg) is the ionic strength, m (mol/kg)
 845 is the molality, ν_M and ν_X are the number of cations and anions of the salt, ν is the number of
 846 ions, $\beta_{MX}^{(0)}$, $\beta_{MX}^{(1)}$, and C_{MX}^ϕ are adjustable parameters (with values of 0.07525, 0.2769 and 0.0014,
 847 respectively), α is a constant (2 for univalent ions), and b is a universal parameter (1.2 kg^{1/2}mol⁻
 848 ^{1/2}).

849

850

851

852

853

856 Figure B-1. EES diagram window of the FO-MED simulation tool. Solved for $T_s = 100$ °C, 16 effects, $\dot{m}_d=100$ m³/d, RR=30%

Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: